

strong aya

A new, interdisciplinary, multi-stakeholder European network to improve healthcare services, research and outcomes for Adolescents and Young Adults with cancer.

The future of cancer therapy

UNIVERSITY OF LEEDS

Deliverable Report

WP1 – Report on the initial Core Outcome Set

Deliverable 1.2

Report on the initial Core Outcome Set

Due date of deliverable: 30/09/2023

Actual submission date: 28/03/2024

Project:	STRONG-AYA
Lead Contributor	UOS- Kirsty Way, Anne-Sophie Darlington, Nicole Collaço
Email	A.Darlington@soton.ac.uk
Other Contributors	NKI – Silvie Janssen
Emails	sh.janssen@nki.nl

Due date	30 09 2023
Delivery date	28 03 2024
Deliverable type	R
Dissemination level	PU

Description of Work	Version	Date
	V1.0	27/03/2024

Description:

This report contains the initial Core Outcome Set, including the methodology that took place for its development. Results from the literature review, qualitative interviews, Delphi survey rounds as well as the consensus meeting have been reported to show the pragmatic decision-making processes behind the development of the Initial COS

summary (max ½ page)

The aim of Work Package 1 (WP1) of STRONG AYA is to develop a Core Outcome Set (COS) for adolescents and young adults (AYAs) with cancer. There is specific scientific methodology that must be followed to develop a COS [1-4], as well as identify the measurements instruments to measure the items in the COS [5]. The stages for making decisions on the final outcomes to be included in a COS are three-fold: (1) A review of the literature to discover which outcomes are important for AYAs with cancer, (2) qualitative interviews with stakeholders (AYA patients, their caregivers, and healthcare professionals) to hear their perceptions of what outcomes are important for AYAs with cancer, (3) consensus methodology, known as a Delphi study.

Following a review of the literature and qualitative interviews, a total of 129 outcomes were accumulated and considered important for AYAs with cancer. These 129 outcomes were then categorised in accordance with Dodd's 38-item taxonomy for outcomes in medical research [6], which formed the skeleton of the Delphi survey. The Delphi survey has a total of three rounds, which aims to come to a consensus between stakeholder groups on which outcomes are the utmost important to measure for AYAs with cancer. Following the first two rounds of the Delphi survey, a total of 61 items met the inclusion criteria (outcomes that received $\geq 70\%$ respondents rating it as a 7-9 on the Likert-scale) and were taken forward to a consensus meeting, which involved 12 members of the STRONG AYA consortium forming an expert panel to make pragmatic decisions on the final outcomes to be included in the Initial COS.

The Initial COS consists of 21 domains; there are 15 CORE domains, 3 ON TREATMENT domains and 3 OFF TREATMENT domains. The development of the Core Measurement Set to supplement the initial COS is still being developed. Round 3 of the Delphi survey is still ongoing; results from the third and final Delphi round will be used to inform the Final COS. In the meantime, the Initial COS will be implemented throughout the healthcare research ecosystem in future work packages in the STRONG AYA project

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2 Definitions

STRONG AYA consortium members are referred to as following within this text:

1. **NKI-AVL** – Stichting het Nederlands Kanker Instituut – Antoni van Leeuwenhoek Ziekenhuis (NL)
2. **YCE** – Youth Cancer Europe (RO)
3. **INT** – Fondazione IRCCS Istituto Nazionale dei Tumori (IT)
4. **FFUND** – FFUND BV (NL)
5. **CLB** – Centre de Lutte Contre le Cancer Leon Berard (FR)
6. **ECO** – European Cancer Organisation (BE)
7. **UNIMAAS** – Universiteit Maastricht (NL)
8. **IKNL** – Stichting Integraal Kankercentrum Nederland (NL)
9. **EORTC** – European Organisation for Research and Treatment of Cancer AISBL (BE)
10. **IGR** – Institut Gustave Roussy (FR)
11. **MSCNRIO** – Narodowy Instytut Onkologii im. Marii Skłodowskiej-Curie – Państwowy Instytut Badawczy (Marie Skłodowska-Curie National Research Institute of Oncology) (PL)
12. **UOM** – University of Manchester (UK)
13. **UOL** – University of Leeds (UK)
14. **LTHT** – Leeds Teaching Hospitals National Health Service Trust (UL)
15. **SOUTHAMPTON** – University of Southampton (UK)

- **Grant Agreement** (including its annexes and amendments): the agreement signed between the beneficiaries of the HORIZON Research and Innovations Actions (hereafter referred to as Horizon) and the European Health and Digital Executive Agency (hereafter referred to as HADEA) for the undertaking of the STRONG AYA project (Grant Agreement no. 101057482).
- **Beneficiary**: Signatories of the Grant Agreement
- **Associated Partner**: Entities which participate in the action but without the right to charge costs or claim contributions.
- **Project**: the sum of all activities carried out in the framework of the Grant Agreement.
- **Consortium**: the STRONG AYA consortium, including all the aforementioned partners.
- **Consortium Agreement**: The agreement made between STRONG AYA members for the implementation and execution of the action outlined in the Grant Agreement. The agreement shall not affect the parties' obligations to HADEA on behalf of the European Union, and/or to one another arising from the Grant Agreement.

3 Abbreviations

Acronym/Abbreviation	Meaning
HCP	Health Care Provider
PRO	Patient Reported Outcome
PROM	Patient Reported Outcome Measure
COS	Core Outcome Set
WP	Work Package
WPL	Work Package Lead(s)
WP1	Work Package 1 (Development Core Outcome Set AYA with cancer & data collection)
WP2	Work Package 2 (Governance, Data Security and Ethics)
WP3	Work Package 3 (Infrastructure and Interoperability)
WP4	Work Package 4 (Operation of STRONG AYA ecosystems, stakeholder and patient involvement, dissemination, exploitation, communication)
WP5	Work Package 5 (Scientific coordination and project management)
KPI	Key Performance Indicator
OA	Open Access
PAB	Patient Advisory Board
EC	European Commission
HADEA	European Health and Digital Executive Agency
SC	Steering Committee
MT	Management Team

4 Introduction

4.1 Project background

Cancer at adolescent and young adult (AYA) age is rare, although 4-6 times more frequent than paediatric cancer (i.e. prepubescent period). However, this rarity does not reflect the significant personal and societal costs of cancer in this population, as reflected in the potential years of life lost or saved, the decreased productivity and quality-of-life due to the impact of the disease during formative years, and the long-term complications or disabilities¹. AYAs with cancer form a unique group; they face age-specific issues (e.g. Infertility, unemployment, financial problems) and decreased quality of life due to cancer and its treatment. Unlike dedicated healthcare and trials for paediatric cancer patients, AYA-specific healthcare services are scarce and vary across Europe. AYAs who are at the core of society and economy need access to age-appropriate and high-quality healthcare.

Defining AYAs with cancer as 15 to 39 years at initial cancer diagnosis², their annual cancer incidence is 42.2/100.000, with 156.431 cases in Europe and 1.231.007 cases worldwide reported in 2018 (together 6.8% of all cancers)³. Population-based data from 27 European countries supports that AYAs have lower survival than children but higher than adults affected by cancer. Advances in cancer treatment have led to increased survival rates for AYAs with cancer, improving by 82% for all cancers between 1990 and 2007⁴.

However, survival improvement in AYA is more challenging than for children and older cancer survivors, which might be due to the fact that AYA have the highest absolute excess risk of second primary malignant neoplasms⁵. AYA face some distinct challenges given that they do not belong to neither paediatric nor adult oncology groups. Characteristic features of this population group include unique spectrum of cancer types, different tumour biology, unique complex psychological needs, distinct late sequelae, including impaired fertility, and palliative care. These traits imply that clinical management, treatment, diagnosis, psychological support will need to be designed and developed for AYA's specific needs. For example, AYAs diagnosed with breast and prostate carcinomas have worse survival than older patients because of the biological differences between them, highlighting the need to target screening methodologies, treatment and policies to their needs⁶. AYAs with cancer also face significant psychological challenges, including substance abuse, mental health issues, suicidal ideations and increased emotional burden from cancer and cancer-related morbidity. Finally, tailoring cancer care to AYA's needs is difficult and due to many different complex factors including the low rate of participation by AYAs in clinical trials and cancer research⁷.

¹ Stoneham SJ. AYA survivorship: The next challenge. *Cancer* 2020; 126: 2116-2119.

² Adolescent and Young Adult Oncology Review Group. Closing the gap: Research and Care Imperatives for Adolescents and Young Adults with Cancer. National Institute of Health, National Cancer Institute, and Livestrong Young Adult Alliance: Bethesda, MD, USA, 2006.

³ Trama A, Botta L, Steliarova-Foucher E. Cancer Burden in Adolescents and Young Adults: A Review of Epidemiological Evidence. *Cancer J* 2018; 24: 256-266

⁴ Trama A, Botta L, Foschi R et al. Survival of European adolescents and young adults diagnosed with cancer in 2000-07: population-based data from EUROCARE-5. *Lancet Oncol* 2016; 17: 896-906.

⁵ Keegan THM, Bleyer A, Rosenberg AS et al. Second Primary Malignant Neoplasms and Survival in Adolescent and Young Adult Cancer Survivors. *JAMA Oncol* 2017; 3: 1554-1557.

⁶ Stark D, Bielack S, Brugieres L et al. Teenagers and young adults with cancer in Europe: from national programmes to a European integrated coordinated project. *European Journal of Cancer Care*, 25(3), 419-427.

⁷ Hayashi RJ. Adolescent and young adult cancer survivorship: The new frontier for investigation. *Cancer* 2019; 125: 1976-1978.

Despite the increasing awareness and a growing body of the scientific literature, these unique issues remain to be fully recognised and addressed by the European health systems and AYAs with cancer are frequently underserved. In part, this may have resulted from the traditional dichotomy between the integrated paediatric (“patient/family-centred”) care services versus dispersed (“disease- centered”) adult oncology services^{8,9,10}. Up to half of AYAs with cancer report unmet informational and service needs, impacting their direct (survival rates) and indirect (long term effects and mental health) recovery to participate in society¹¹.

Furthermore, aligned with this barrier is the low rate of health care utilisation by AYAs, especially primary care, given their challenges to sustain health insurance coverage¹². According to a survey conducted through the networks of the AYA Working Group of the European Society for Medical Oncology (ESMO) and the European Society for Paediatric Oncology (SIOP Europe), 67% of practitioners do not have access to specialised centres for AYA with cancer, 67% had no access to a specialist cancer service for late effects management and 38% had no access to fertility specialists. Under-provision and inequality of AYA cancer care is common across Europe and especially in the Eastern and Southern-East. Furthermore, the Working Group also reported an absence of outcome measures for monitoring and evaluating AYA cancer care programs and control¹³.

Among the recommended future steps, it has been identified that one of the most important contributions to AYA research would be to pool data (e.g. patient-reported outcomes, clinical and treatment data) across institutions and countries and create large cohorts for researchers to Address the burden of cancer in AYA¹⁴. There is a lack of data standardization, data interoperability and (prospective) collection of outcomes of relevance for AYAs with cancer.

The STRONG-AYA project aims to tackle the underrepresentation of AYA’s experiences and outcomes when navigating the healthcare system and in clinical care by developing national infrastructures for outcome data management and clinical decision-making within a pan-European ecosystem and establishing communication feedback for AYAs with cancer and the healthcare systems. This will be key to improving healthcare services, research, outcomes and policies for AYAs and to ultimately better cancer care for this patient group.

To this aim, STRONG-AYA brings together an international multi-disciplinary consortium across seven European countries, led by the Netherlands Cancer Institute (NKI) and composed of academic research organisations (European Organisation for Research and Treatment of Cancer (EORTC), University of Southampton, University of Leeds, University of Manchester, Maastricht University, Netherlands Comprehensive Cancer Organisation (IKNL)), clinical partners (Italian National Tumour Institute, Léon Bérard Centre, Gustave Roussy Institute, Maria Skłodowska-Curie National Research Institute of Oncology, the Leeds Teaching Hospitals National Health Service Trust), stakeholder and patient organisations (Youth Cancer Europe, European Cancer Organisation) and a consulting company (FFUND).

⁸ Ferrari A, Stark D, Peccatori FA et al. Adolescents and young adults (AYA) with cancer: a position paper from the AYA Working Group of the European Society for Medical Oncology (ESMO) and the European Society for Paediatric Oncology (SIOP). ESMO Open 2021; 6: 100096.

⁹ Osborn M, Johnson R, Thompson K et al. Models of care for adolescent and young adult cancer programs. *Pediatr Blood Cancer* 2019; 66: e27991.

¹⁰ Fardell JE, Patterson P, Wakefield CE et al. A Narrative Review of Models of Care for Adolescents and Young Adults with Cancer: Barriers and Recommendations. *J Adolesc Young Adult Oncol* 2018; 7: 148-152.

¹¹ Keegan TH, Lichtensztajn DY, Kato I et al. Unmet adolescent and young adult cancer survivors information and service needs: a population-based cancer registry study. *J Cancer Surviv* 2012; 6: 239-250.

¹² Hayashi RJ. Adolescent and young adult cancer survivorship: The new frontier for investigation. *Cancer* 2019; 125: 1976-1978.

¹³ Saloustros E, Stark D, Michailidou K et al. Report on ESMO/SIOPE European Landscape project key results: Mapping the status and needs in AYA cancer care. Late-breaking and deferred publication abstracts public health 2017; 28, 5: V643.

¹⁴ Smith AW, Seibel NL, Lewis DR et al. Next steps for adolescent and young adult oncology workshop: An update on progress and recommendations for the future. *Cancer* 2016; 122: 988-999.

Building on previous initiatives, a STRONG-AYA data ecosystem will be set up for value-based care, research and policy for AYA with cancer by:

1. **Developing a Core Outcome Set (COS)** specifically for AYAs with cancer, via a participative consensus process defining most important aspects for those directly affected by AYA cancer, including patients and healthcare professionals.
2. **Implementing the COS across several national European healthcare systems.** Data will be collected at local level and will then be included in a data integration platform. An overall ecosystem framework for data analytics and output will be created supporting federated analyses and the creation of reports across clinical and patient-reported data and making national repositories of (patient-reported) health data, available to individual patients, patient organisations, regulatory authorities, as well as the patients' health care providers to inform clinical decision-making. The five resulting **national ecosystems** will be connected to each other into **the pan-European ecosystem** using a federated approach also utilizing the overall ecosystem framework.
3. **Disseminating the COS to a wide range of local as well as pan-European stakeholders,** in particular by developing analytical tools to process and present patient outcome data and establish feedback loops that inform patients and clinicians.

Implementing these project objectives are five work packages within the STRONG-AYA project:

- WP1: Development Core Outcome Set AYA with cancer and Data Collection (Lead: SOUTHAMPTON)
- WP2: Governance, Data Security and Ethics (Lead: EORTC)
- WP3: Infrastructure and Interoperability (Lead: UNIMAAS)
- WP4: Operation of STRONG-AYA ecosystems, Stakeholder and Patient involvement, Dissemination, Exploitation, Communication (Lead: E.C.O.)
- WP5: Scientific Coordination and Project Management (Lead: NKI)

STRONG-AYA will enable AYA care and research to benefit from collection and pooling of patient-centered data and collaboration among all stakeholders: patients, healthcare professionals, scientists, and policymakers. More widely, the project will leverage the network of interested organisations and networks established under STRONG-AYA for long-term strengthened promotion of the necessary implementation of specialist AYA cancer services across Europe. This will ultimately bring novel insights into AYA cancer care, research and policy, contributing to the long-term improvement of outcomes for people with AYA cancer.

4.2 Deliverable introduction

WP1 (developing a Core Outcome Set): The overall aim of WP1 is to develop a Core Outcome Set (COS) for AYAs with cancer. We aim to assess which outcomes, including patient-reported outcomes, clinical, and treatment related outcomes, are most important to measure for AYAs with cancer, from the point of view of AYAs with cancer, their caregivers, healthcare professionals, researchers and policymakers. The process for developing a COS is outlined in several guidance documents, and follows a clear process [1-4]. This includes adhering to the 11 minimum standards of Core Outcome Set-STAndards for Development (COS-STAD) [2] and the 13 items considered essential documentation as described in the Core Outcome Set-STANDARDISED Protocol Items (COS-STAP) [3].

This deliverable aims to report on the development of the Initial COS, focusing on Phase 5 of the COS development which was published in the COS protocol paper: *determine “what” to measure – the outcomes in the COS* [7]. This phase has 3 steps to arrive at the final COS: 1) a review of the literature to identify relevant outcomes for AYAs with cancer, 2) qualitative interviews with AYAs with cancer/who have had a diagnosis of cancer, parents/partners/siblings and healthcare professionals who provide care to AYAs to generate a complete list of outcomes of relevance to AYAs with cancer, and 3) conducting a Delphi study. A thorough description of the Initial COS, supplemented with the initial Core Measurement Set, will be provided. Further refinements to the Initial COS and Core Measurement set will take place throughout the remainder of the STRONG AYA project.

5 Developing the initial Core Outcome Set

Background

Cancer patients in any healthcare system should have access to high-quality care to ensure good outcomes in terms of survival and health-related quality of life (HRQoL) [8, 9]. This is particularly important for adolescents and young adults with cancer (AYAs), defined here as those aged 15 to 39 years at initial cancer diagnosis. AYAs are distinct from younger and older cancer populations based on their unique spectrum of cancer types, as well as the developmental milestones they will be undergoing during this age range [10, 11]. AYAs require access to oncology services that provide expert cancer care and consider their age-specific and complex psychosocial and physical needs. Although an ever-increasing amount of data is available, the collection, access, and use of these data are still very fragmented within, and especially across, national healthcare systems. There is a lack of international data standardization, data interoperability and prospective collection of outcomes of relevance for AYAs that are important for informing decision-making. Thus, the field needs a core outcome set (COS), derived from a multi-stakeholder consensus-based process, that includes the minimum set of AYA-specific outcomes and associated high quality measures of those outcomes [7].

Coming to a decision, or a consensus, on what outcomes are most important to measure for AYAs with cancer to then form a COS is a rigorous, scientific process. This report will describe the process of developing a Core Outcome Set (COS) for AYAs with cancer, including the identification of relevant outcomes and a consensus process, which resulted in the development of the initial COS for the STRONG AYA project.

Methods

The development of the COS for AYAs with cancer was informed by existing methodological standards of the Core Outcome Measures in Effectiveness Trials (COMET) initiative [1], and the International Consortium for Health Outcomes Measurement (ICHOM) [4]. An adapted, combined methodology that captures all methodological standards of both COMET and ICHOM was implemented, as presented in Figure 1:

Figure 1: the seven phases of the AYA COS development [7]

Phase 1: Scope definition

The scope for a COS for AYAs with cancer was defined in the opinion paper, previously published [8]. It was described that receiving a cancer diagnosis during the ages of 15-39 can interfere with developmental milestones, including forming identity, establishing autonomy, responsibility and independence, education and starting a career, romantic relationships, and starting a family [10, 12]. Therefore, one of the most important contributions to AYA research was identified to be a pool of data (eg, patient-reported outcomes, clinical and treatment data) across institutions and countries, to create large cohorts for researchers to address the burden of cancer in AYA [13]; this would be in the form of a COS. Outcomes in the COS must be meaningful and relevant, and should focus on what matters to the AYA population, specifically the patients.

Phase 2: Establishing the need for a COS for AYAs

According to the COMET database, there is no COS available or being developed for AYAs (July 15 2022).

Phase 3: Composition of AYA Working Group

As described in the protocol paper [7], the Working Group consists of a steering committee and a project advisory group (PAG). The steering committee are responsible for the management of the project. Work Package 1 is responsible for the development of the COS. The PAG consists of international experts (AYAs and their caregivers/representatives, health care practitioners from different disciplines, researchers,

regulators, policy makers and all other important decision-makers). They have formed a vital role in the development of the Delphi survey and feeding back on the first draft of the Initial COS.

Phase 4: Study protocol development

The COS development protocol was created according to the 13 items considered essential documentation as described in the COS-STAP [30] and the 11 minimum standards for COS-STAD (Figure 2).

Table 1 Developing the COS process based on the COMET COS-STAD

Domain	Standard number	Methodology	Application in the proposed project
Scope specification	1	The research or practice setting for the COS	Research and clinical practice
	2	The health condition covered by the COS	Cancer
	3	The population covered by the COS	AYAs aged 13–39 years at initial cancer diagnosis and inclusive of the whole cancer care continuum
	4	The interventions covered by the COS	All
Stakeholders involved	5	Those who will use the COS in research	Researchers, policy-makers dealing with AYAs
	6	Healthcare professionals with experience of patients with the condition	Clinicians (e.g. medical oncologists), nurse specialists, applied healthcare professionals
	7	Patients with the condition or their representatives	Adolescents and young adults aged 13–39 years at first cancer diagnosis, their informal caregivers or advocates
Consensus process	8	Long-list of outcomes considered by stakeholders	Literature review and interviews with stakeholders
	9	Scoring process and consensus definition	Delphi scoring using a nine-point Likert scale (1–3, limited importance; 4–6, not crucial importance; 7–9, crucial importance) Consensus criteria: score of 7+ per item by ≥ 70% of respondents
	10	Criteria for including/eliminating outcomes	Inclusion: outcomes scored 'critically important' by ≥ 70% AND 'not important' by < 15% of participants Exclusion: outcomes scored 'critically important' from less than 50% of participants
	11	Avoiding language ambiguity in the description of outcomes	Plain language version will be available, informed by interviews and pilot-tested with patients

Figure 2: Developing the COS process based on the COMET COS-STAD [7]

Phase 5: Determine “what” to measure – the outcomes in the COS

The process involved in determining “what” to measure / the outcomes in the COS was three-fold (Figure 3):

- (1) A review of the literature to identify relevant outcomes for AYAs with cancer
- (2) Qualitative interviews with AYAs with cancer/who have had a diagnosis of cancer, parents/partners/siblings and healthcare professionals who provide care to AYAs to generate a complete list of outcomes of relevance to AYAs with cancer
- (3) Conducting a Delphi study, to make final decision on the outcomes to be included in the COS

Figure 3: Methodology for identifying “what” to measure in the COS (based on recommendation from the COMET Initiative [1])

Step 1: Literature Review

A literature review was conducted to identify and extract relevant outcomes for AYAs with cancer. The following databases were searched: Medline ALL, Embase, Web of Science Core Collection, Cochrane Central Register of Controlled Trials, and additional search engines (Google Scholar). The search string for each database was constructed together with an experienced librarian. The following inclusion and exclusion criteria were applied:

Table 1: Inclusion / exclusion criteria for the Literature Review

Inclusion criteria	Exclusion criteria
Population: AYAs (13 up until (and including) 39 years old at initial cancer diagnosis) or a subset of this age range (e.g. adolescents or young adults only).	Study population consisted exclusively of healthy or non-cancer study population, including desmoids and in situ carcinomas
Studies conducted in other study populations, such as healthcare providers, friends, parents or carers of AYAs will be included only if the participants provide information on the outcomes of AYAs.	Study population consisted exclusively of childhood cancer patients aged under 13 years at initial cancer diagnosis or adult cancer patients aged over 39 years at initial cancer diagnosis

On and/or of treatment, including at diagnosis, during treatment or following treatment (patients and/or survivors). There was no upper limit for the time since diagnosis for AYA cancer survivors. Patients on maintenance treatment were be included.	Study protocols, case reports, reviews/ meta-analyses, expert opinions, theoretical papers, policy documents/ guidelines, consensus letters, editorials
Written in English language	Full text unavailable
Any type of malignant tumour or benign central nervous system (CNS) tumour	Non-human study
Study types: randomized controlled trials (RCTs), observational cohort studies, case-control studies, case series, cross-sectional studies, qualitative studies	
Studies focussing on all types of biological, physical, psychological or social outcomes	

Each article was independently screened by two reviewers based on title/abstract and full text, using the selection criteria outlined above. Conflicts were resolved through discussion or, if necessary, by involving a third reviewer from the steering committee to arrive at majority agreement. The following data was extracted: study characteristics, outcomes, outcome measurement instruments, potential case-mix variables (e.g. sex, ethnicity, type of treatment) as preliminary work for *Phase 7—determine “case-mix “ factors.*

Step 2: Qualitative interviews with stakeholders

To further investigate the relevant outcomes for AYAs with cancer, semi-structured interviews were carried out with the following stakeholder groups:

1. AYAs who received a cancer diagnosis between the ages of 15-39 years
2. Parents / caregivers / spouses / siblings of AYAs
3. Healthcare professionals (HCPs), who provide care for AYAs

Participant recruitment for the qualitative interviews

Purposive sampling, aiming for diversity, was conducted in the following ways:

Table 2. Recruitment pathways for interviews

AYAs	Parents / caregivers / Partners / siblings	Healthcare professionals
<p>Youth Cancer Europe charity: contact at charity emailed potential participants.</p> <p>Youth Cancer Europe advertised study through social media channels (LinkedIn, Facebook).</p>	<p>Asking each AYA interviewed if their parent/partner/sibling would take part in an interview.</p>	<p>(Inter)national AYA oncology networks (via ENTYAC, ESMO-SIOPE)) by email/newsletter.</p>
<p>Twitter post (hosted by research group’s Twitter page at University of Southampton) and retweeted by others.</p>	<p>Contact at Cancer charity centre in UK recruited (gave out PIS for study) eligible participants that go to the centre.</p>	<p>Participants interviewed recommended other professionals to potentially approach for participation.</p>
<p>Social media (Facebook group) of youth cancer group through a lead cancer hospital Trust in the UK.</p>	<p>UK cancer support groups/charities (Ovacome Family/friends support group, CancerWise, Carers Support Wessex Sussex support group, Live Through This peer support group, Haematology Transplant Patient Family Group).</p>	<p>EORTC sent email about study to their members.</p>
<p>Participants interviewed directed other AYAs to take part in an interview.</p>	<p>Dutch cancer carer networks.</p>	

Interview guide

Participants were initially asked their demographic information, including their age sex, nationality, ethnicity and diagnosis (for AYAs / caregivers). HCPs were also asked for their profession, years’ experience, and their core expertise within their profession. Following this, open-ended questions were asked regarding what outcomes they consider important for AYAs with cancer. AYAs were asked to discuss their experiences of having cancer; parents / caregivers were asked what the AYA experienced whilst having cancer; HCPs were asked what outcomes are especially important for AYAs with cancer. Prompts were provided, including domains such as: physical functioning, emotional functioning, social functioning, delivery of care, physiological/clinical outcomes, and overall quality of life.

Interview data collection

Interviews were conducted via Microsoft Teams. They were audio recorded and transcribed verbatim, upon the participant’s consent. Recordings were analysed descriptively using thematic content analysis,

in which outcomes were extracted and categorized into relevant domains. Outcomes were counted to identify weight of domains.

The Delphi process

The Delphi technique is a multistage process, designed to transform opinion into consensus by iterative rounds of questionnaires, interspersed with controlled feedback [14]. Anonymity of individual panel members within specific stakeholder groups removes inherent bias, such as group conformity, as participants do not interact directly with each other, so situations where the group is dominated by the views of certain individuals can be avoided [15]. Delphi studies are typically 2-3 rounds, although aspects of its methodology can be interpreted in a variety of ways.

Delphi survey development

The outcomes identified as relevant for AYAs with cancer via the review of the literature (*step 1*) and the qualitative interviews (*step 2*) formed an initial list, which would be taken forward to the first round of the Delphi survey. The initial list of outcomes were categorized using Dodd’s 38-item taxonomy for outcomes in medical research [6], and formed the skeleton of the Delphi survey (Table 3). The taxonomy was adapted, in terms of order of outcomes and specific wording, to adjust for the lay audience of this Delphi survey. The ordering of domains in the taxonomy was also adjusted to improve the coherence of the survey, for the purposes of the Delphi.

Table 3: The skeleton of the Delphi survey, using an adapted version of Dodd’s 38-item taxonomy for outcomes in medical research [6]

Dodd’s 38-item taxonomy for outcomes in medical research
Outcomes of disease
Mortality/survival
Physiological/clinical
Outcomes relating to neoplasms
Cardiac outcomes
Circulation (blood, vascular and lymphatic system) outcomes
Respiratory system (chest and lungs) outcomes
Stomach (gastrointestinal) and digestion outcomes
Nervous system outcomes
Kidney and urinary system outcomes
Liver and pancreas (hepatobiliary) outcomes
Immune system outcomes
Infection outcomes
Ear, hearing, and balance outcomes
Eyes and vision outcomes
Skin and subcutaneous tissue outcomes
Musculoskeletal and connective tissue outcomes
Nutrition and metabolism outcomes
Injury and poisoning outcomes

Musculoskeletal and connective tissue outcomes
Hormones (endocrine system) outcomes
Reproductive system outcomes
Pregnancy and childbirth (before, during and after childbirth) outcomes
Genetic outcomes
Psychiatric outcomes
General outcomes
Functioning
Physical functioning
Social functioning
Role Functioning
Emotional and Psychological Functioning / Wellbeing
Cognitive Functioning
Global Quality of Life
Perceived Health Status
Delivery of Care
Personal Circumstances
Resource Use
Economic
Hospital
Need for further intervention
Societal and carer burden
Adverse events / effects

Draft versions of the survey items were evaluated by 8 members of the STRONG AYA consortium, including work package leads (n = 2), researchers (n=2) and HCPs (n = 4). This was to ensure all outcomes were: (1) phrased in layman’s terms to ensure participants could accurately interpret them, and (2) categorized correctly according to the taxonomy. The length of the survey was highlighted as an overarching concern; therefore, efforts were made to eliminate any potential repetitiveness in outcome items and thus reduce the overall number of items to be included.

The final list of outcomes, as well as the survey instructions, were pilot tested by three researchers within the STRONG AYA consortium, and feedback was provided. This was to test the usability of the survey platform, as well as the interpretations of each outcome.

Recruitment for the Delphi survey

The Delphi process was comprised of three expert stakeholder panels:

- (4) AYAs (aged 15-39 at diagnosis) **and** caregivers (including parents / guardians, family members, partners and caregivers).
- (5) Healthcare professionals who provide care for AYAs with cancer.
- (6) Researchers **and** policymakers who are active in the field of AYAs with cancer.

The recruitment target for the Delphi survey was 100 participants per stakeholder group (300 in total). This would allow for drop-out rates moving into subsequent Delphi rounds. Recruitment materials were developed, including a 1-Page recruitment letter outlining the study, email templates, and social media adverts. Participants for each stakeholder group were recruited in the following ways:

Table 4: Description of the recruitment strategies for each stakeholder group in the Delphi surveys

(1) AYAs and Caregivers	(2) Healthcare professionals	(3) Researchers and policymakers
AYAs and caregivers that took part in the qualitative interviews were asked if they would also like to take part in the Delphi survey.	Healthcare professionals that took part in the qualitative interviews were asked if they would also like to take part in the Delphi survey.	Researchers were contacted via their email addresses which were found in recent publications in AYA journals (e.g. Journal of Adolescent and Young Adult Oncology).
Youth Cancer Europe are a charity made up of youth cancer organisations across Europe. A contact at the charity contacted potential participants to invite them to take part in the Delphi survey. They also advertised through social media channels (LinkedIn, Facebook).	The European Society for Paediatric Oncology (SIOPE) is a pan-European organisation representing all professionals working in the field of childhood and AYA cancers. They shared the recruitment letter with all members of the European Network for Teenagers and Young Adults with Cancer (ENTYAC).	Researchers provided contact details for other researchers who may wish to take part.
The Youth and Cancer Foundation (Stichting Jongeren en Kanker) is a patient organisation for AYAs with cancer. They shared the social media adverts via their Instagram and Facebook stories.	The European Cancer Organisation (ECO) are network of oncology professionals and cancer patients. They advertised the Delphi survey in their monthly newsletter.	The European Cancer Organisation (ECO) are network of oncology professionals and cancer patients. They advertised the Delphi survey in their monthly newsletter.
The European Cancer Organisation (ECO) are network of oncology professionals and cancer patients. They advertised the Delphi survey in their monthly newsletter.	Participants shared with their networks of HCPs at local hospitals.	
Participants directed other AYAs and caregivers to take part, through word of mouth	HCPs alerted their AYA patient community, via community patient groups and local charities.	

or advertisements in their local cancer communities.		
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Survey data collection procedure

The online survey platform used to collect responses was Qualtrics (<https://www.qualtrics.com/uk/>).

The participant information sheet was provided at the start of the survey, as well as a checkbox for participants to provide their consent for taking part. Participants were reminded of their right to withdraw from the study at any time, privacy and accessibility information, and how their data will be used.

Initial, generic demographic questions (relevant to *all* stakeholder groups) were included at the start of the survey to collect information, such as: age, gender, ethnicity, country of residence, education, and socioeconomic status. Specific demographic questions relevant to separate stakeholder groups were then asked. For example, AYAs were asked about their diagnosis type, age at diagnosis, treatment status, and clinic-type. Caregivers were asked the same questions, in relation to the AYAs they care for. HCPs, researchers and policymakers were asked questions relating to their profession, years' experience, and their expertise within their profession.

Our Delphi process included three survey rounds:

- (1) Initial item rating, with all 129-outcomes
- (2) Item re-rating, with feedback from previous survey round
- (3) Item ranking, choosing a top 15 outcomes for on and off treatment*

** Round 3 of the Delphi survey is currently underway at the time of this report*

Round 1 of the Delphi Survey

Following demographic questions, the survey asked participants to rate the importance all 129 outcomes on a 9-point Likert Scale, as per recommendations outlined by the GRADE working group [16]. A rating scale of “not important” (rating of 1–3), “important, but not critical” (rating of 4–6), or “extremely important / critical” (rating 7–9) was provided. An option for “unable to answer” was also provided. It was explained to participants that they should not rate too many outcomes as “extremely important”, as the end-goal was to have only approximately 10-15 outcomes that are kept for inclusion in the final COS. Participants were reminded on each page of the survey that they should rate the outcomes with emphasis on the AYA (aged 15-39) demographic, to avoid resulting in a COS that is not specific to the AYA age-group.

Participants were required to provide a rating for every item in the survey. At the end of the survey was an open-text box for participants to provide any outcomes they thought were missing in the survey, that were important to measure for AYAs with cancer.

Translations of the survey were provided for the following languages: Dutch, French, Italian, German, Spanish and Polish. This was to increase the reach and cultural diversity of the Delphi survey.

Round 2 of the Delphi Survey

The second survey round included the same initial demographic questions as round 1. Participants were provided with a personalised URL, therefore their responses to the demographic questions were saved and carried forward from round 1 and they were able to make changes (if necessary).

The concept of a second Delphi survey round is to provide feedback to participants of the results from round 1, and allow them to potentially change their rating on the 9-point Likert scale, to begin a convergence of opinion (consensus) and come to an agreement on the most important outcomes to measure for AYAs with cancer. Feedback from round 1 was provided as a percentage above each number on the Likert scale (i.e. a percentage of how many other participants in their stakeholder group rated the outcome as X level of importance). Participants were also provided with their original rating from round 1 as a pre-filled dot on the Likert scale. See Figure 3.

All items listed in round 1 of the Delphi survey were carried forward to round 2. Participants were also asked to rate six additional outcomes that participants had listed as important yet missing from round 1 (using the open text box).

Figure 3: A snapshot of round 2 of the Delphi survey, evidencing the use of feedback (%) and previewing participant’s round 1 responses.

Consensus meeting

In order for an Initial COS to be developed in time to begin implementation of data collection throughout the healthcare research ecosystem for the STRONG AYA project, a consensus meeting was scheduled prior to conducting Round 3 of the Delphi survey. This was to allow decisions to be made regarding the outcomes to be included in the initial COS. This meeting took place on 18/01/2024 and attendees included 12 participants from the STRONG AYA consortium, who formed an expert panel.

All outcomes that received ≥70% respondents rating it as a 7-9 on the Likert-scale, across all stakeholder groups, were presented to the expert panel. Based on discussions regarding the difficulty of distinguishing

the most important outcomes for AYAs with cancer, it was decided that the initial COS would identify outcomes for both ON and OFF treatment phases. The definitions for ON and OFF treatment were as follows:

On treatment = a cancer patient receiving curative treatment, including maintenance treatment, who is not believed to be disease-free.

Off treatment = a cancer patient treated with curative intent, who is disease-free, or receiving life-extending or palliative treatment / care

An online poll took place (using a polling platform, Vevox) whereby participants were asked to select the most important 15 outcomes to measure for AYAs with cancer for both ON and OFF treatment. The number “15” was decided following exploration of the literature and averaging the number of COS items of cancer COS published since 2020.

Results from this meeting were used to inform the first draft of the Initial COS. This draft of the Initial COS was circulated to the STRONG AYA consortium, plus members of the public advisory board for feedback. Feedback was provided from 7 researchers and HCPs in the STRONG AYA consortium and 4 patient advisory board members.

Round 3 of the Delphi Survey

Round 3 aims for participants to be more succinct with their decision making. Any outcome that received $\geq 70\%$ respondents rating it as a 7-9 on the Likert-scale was carried forward to round 3 of the Delphi process, per stakeholder group. For example., the AYA and parent/caregiver stakeholder panel were only presented with the list of outcomes that received $\geq 70\%$ respondents rating it as a 7-9 on the Likert-scale by their stakeholder group (see Table 6) .

Similar to the consensus meeting, participants were asked to identify the top 15 outcomes for AYAs with cancer, whilst both ON and OFF treatment. Additionally, they were asked to then rank the top 15 that they chose, in order of “most important” and “least important”, for both ON and OFF treatment. It is hoped that this methodology will elicit greater consensus from stakeholder groups, thus resulting in the Final COS.

Round 3 is currently ongoing at the time of this report, and is due to close within the upcoming weeks. Results from this survey round will then inform the Final COS.

Phase 6: Determine “how” to measure the COS

A joint initiative between the COnsensus-based Standards for the selection of health Measurement INstruments (COSMIN) initiative [5] and the COMET initiative [1] have developed a guideline on how to select measurement instruments for outcomes included in a COS (Figure 4).

Figure 4: Flowchart for the selection of outcome measurement instruments for COS [17]

To develop the Core Measurement Set for the Initial COS, the guidelines proposed in Figure 4 were followed, with the exception of updating / performing a literature search in the absence of a good quality, up-to-date review. The consensus process (*step 4*) will be in the form of a meeting due to take place on 26th March 2024, whereby members of the STRONG AYA consortium from the University of Southampton and NKI will meet to make pragmatic decisions on which are the most suitable measurement tools, in terms of their psychometric properties, accessibility, translation availability, and number of items/subscales.

Once the Final COS has been developed, the scientific process of measurement instrument selection detailed in Figure 4 will be followed extensively.

Determine “case-mix variables”

As part of the data extraction process for the literature review (see section 5.5.1), case mix variables published in the literature were collected. These will then be pooled and analysed, ready for implementation alongside the Initial COS in future work packages in the STRONG AYA project. This process is ongoing at the time of this report.

Results

The Literature Review

A total of 14 reviewers from the STRONG AYA consortium conducted title and abstract screening, and full text screening. 15 reviewers conducted data extraction.

The initial search identified 37127 records through the five databases (Figure 5). After duplicates were removed, the search returned 19826 records. Following screening 17301 records on title and abstracts, 11727 records were excluded. This resulted in 5574 records being assessed for eligibility, from which 2980 were excluded. In total, 2594 studies were included in the reviews; outcomes from these records were collated and informed the development of the Delphi survey. Importantly, refinement of the literature search is still ongoing at the time of this report. The number of articles reported in Figure 5 were accurate for developing an initial list of outcomes for the Delphi survey, however more articles have been excluded since this point, and moving forwards to the write up of the Literature Review.

Figure 5: Flow chart of study screening and inclusion process, according to the PRISMA Framework.

Qualitative Interviews

A total of 56 interviews were conducted between April 2023-June 2023; 27 AYAs, 4 parents / caregivers, and 25 HCPs. Demographic information and results relating to the production of a digital tool for the STRONG AYA project are outlined in Deliverable 1.11. A thematic content analysis resulted in 22 outcome domains that were perceived as important for AYAs with cancer. Table 5 summarises the domains identified in the interviews, including *which* stakeholder group identified *what* as important. These 22 domains, plus the individual outcomes within each domain, were then to inform the production of the Delphi survey.

Table 5: Domain results from the thematic content analysis of the qualitative interviews, per stakeholder group

Domain	AYAs	HCPs	Parents / caregivers
Fertility	X	X	X
Relationships/sexual intimacy	X	X	X
Changes to family dynamics/roles	X	X	X
Mental health/psychological	X	X	X
Identity	X	X	
Social functioning (excl. romantic relationships)	X	X	X
Connecting to other peers with cancer of the same life stage	X		
Education	X	X	X
Work (positive)	X		X
Work (negative)	X	X	
Financial implications	X	X	X
Body image (self-esteem)	X	X	
Survival/mortality	X	X	X
Loss of control		X	
Loss of independence	X	X	X
Long term effects of cancer and treatment/affects post treatment	X	X	
Living with and beyond cancer	X	X	X
Managing impacts on daily routines/lives	X		
Behaviour	X	X	
Healthcare	X	X	X
Physical	X		X
Cognitive	X		

The Delphi survey

Generating the initial list of outcomes

Following data extraction from the literature review and content analysis from the qualitative interviews, a total of 129 outcomes were identified as relevant for AYAs with cancer. These were then categorized according to the adapted version of Dodd’s 38-item taxonomy (see Table 3) and formed the item-list for the Delphi survey.

Participant characteristics

The participation and retention rates for rounds 1 and 2 of the Delphi survey are shown below:

Table 6: Participation and retention statistics for rounds 1 and 2 of the Delphi survey

Stakeholders	Round 1	Group total	Round 2	Group total	Retention
AYAs	72	80	44	48	60.0%
Caregivers	8		4		
HCPs	115	115	90	90	78.3%
Researchers	64	66	46	48	72.7%
Policymakers	2		2		
Total		255		185	72.5%

Importantly, **N=11** AYAs from round 1 and **N=3** AYAs from round 2 were excluded from analysis due to their age at diagnosis being below 15 (they have been removed from the analysis in Table 6)

Achieving consensus

Following round 2 of the Delphi survey, a total of 61 outcomes met the consensus criteria ($\geq 70\%$ respondents rating it as a 7-9 on the Likert-scale) across the three stakeholder groups. Table 7 presents the outcomes that met the inclusion criteria (outcomes that received $\geq 70\%$ respondents rating it as a 7-9 on the Likert-scale) for each stakeholder group.

Table 7: Outcomes that met the consensus criteria, per stakeholder group

Outcome	AYA + Caregivers	HCP	Researchers + Policymakers
Overall survival	X	X	X
Disease-free survival	X	X	X
Disease-specific mortality	X	X	X
All-cause mortality		X	
Cancer progression	X	X	X
Occurrence of second malignancy	X	X	X
Weakened heart / heart failure		X	
Damage to the brain	X	X	X
Immunodeficiency	X		
Life threatening infections	X	X	X
Anxiety	X	X	X
Depression		X	X
PTSD and PTSS	X	X	X
Pain	X	X	X
Fatigue	X	X	X
Weight gain and overweight / obesity		X	
Fertility / infertility	X	X	X
Early menopause		X	X
Risk to pregnancy / baby		X	X
Passing cancer down in family		X	
Functional ability	X	X	X
Ability to carry out self-care	X	X	X
Changes in motor skills		X	
Sexual dysfunction		X	X
Social activity / interaction		X	X
Social isolation		X	X
Impact on making/maintaining friendships			X
Impact on family relationships			X
Romantic relationships and intimacy		X	X
Ability to care for family members		X	
Changes to life goals		X	
Ability to do work / schoolwork		X	X
Loss of job / employment,		X	X
Achieving a full education		X	
Impact on future or current employability		X	
Fear of death		X	
Fear of cancer coming back	X	X	
Ability to cope		X	
Personal independence		X	
Self-esteem and self-confidence		X	
Problems with memory		X	
Lack of concentration / attention	X		
Quality of life	X		

Perception of own health		X	
Carer’s financial and/or time investments		X	X
Impact of disease on others		X	X
Affording the costs of daily living		X	X
Impact of disease on financial income		X	X
Changes in family/partner dynamics		X	X
Adherence to treatment protocols		X	X
Feeling heard by healthcare professional	X	X	
Given choices about treatment and care	X	X	
Given advice and support	X	X	
Opportunity for fertility preservation	X	X	X
Opportunity for visitors at the hospital		X	
Access to mental health support	X	X	X
Participation in clinical trials		X	X
Need for other intervention		X	
Indirect cost of diagnosis,		X	X
Access to the recommended treatment		X	X
Survivorship support		X	X
Total	23	56	37

All 61 outcomes that met the inclusion criteria were taken forward to the consensus meeting held on 18/01/2024. The results of the top 15 ranked outcomes in terms of their importance whilst ON and OFF treatment are shown in Table 8. For the OFF-treatment domain, the 15th ranked outcome was joint between 11 outcomes. The expert panel also decided that “receipt of age-appropriate” was missing from the list but should be included, despite not reaching consensus from the three stakeholder groups in the Delphi survey.

Table 8: Results from the Vevox poll in the consensus meeting

ON treatment		OFF treatment	
Outcome	N (%)	Outcome	N (%)
Overall survival	10 (83.3)	Quality of Life	10 (83.3)
Fertility / infertility	10 (83.3)	Overall survival	9 (75.0)
Pain	10 (83.3)	Fertility / infertility	7 (58.3)
Fatigue	10 (83.3)	Cancer progression	7 (58.3)
Quality of Life	10 (83.3)	Damage to the brain	7 (58.3)
Access to mental health support	10 (83.3)	Access to mental health support	7 (58.3)
Cancer progression	7 (58.3)	Fear of cancer coming back	7 (58.3)
Opportunity for fertility preservation	6 (50.0)	Occurrence of (second) malignancy	6 (50.0)
Ability to do work / schoolwork	6 (50.0)	PTSD and PTSS	6 (50.0)
Feeling heard by HCP	6 (50.0)	Ability to do work / schoolwork	6 (50.0)
Life threatening infections	5 (41.7)	Fatigue	5 (41.7)
Anxiety	5 (41.7)	Romantic relationships and intimacy	5 (41.7)
PTSD and PTSS	5 (41.7)	Changes to life goals	5 (41.7)
Participation in clinical trials	5 (41.7)	Impact of disease on financial income	5 (41.7)
Social activity / interaction	5 (41.7)	Disease-free survival	4 (33.3)
		Sexual dysfunction	4 (33.3)

Opportunity for fertility preservation	4 (33.3)
Weakened heart / heart failure	4 (33.3)
Pain	4 (33.3)
Ability to carry out self-care	4 (33.3)
Maintaining / developing personal independence	4 (33.3)
Social activity / interaction	4 (33.3)
Impact on future or current employability	4 (33.3)
Given advice and support	4 (33.3)

The Initial COS

The decisions on what outcomes / domains to be included in the Initial COS were based primarily on the results of rounds 1 and 2 of the Delphi survey, plus discussion and results from the consensus meeting. Firstly, any outcome that met the consensus criteria across all three stakeholder groups were included in the Initial COS. This is with the exception of the survival / mortality outcomes; instead, it was decided at the consensus meeting that “Overall Survival” would be included to cover all survival/mortality domains. “Occurrence of second malignancy” was also removed from the Initial COS, and instead falls under the umbrella term “Cancer progression”.

After the initial COS was circulated to the STRONG AYA consortium, plus members of the public advisory board for feedback, the addition of “cardiac outcomes” was proposed, as well as grouping of anxiety, depression and PTSD / PTSS to form the outcome “psychological distress”.

Table 9 displays all additions and changes to domain names, as written in the Initial COS.

Table 9: Changes in domains for the Initial COS

Outcome (as per Delphi Survey)	Domain name in Initial COS
Overall survival	
Disease-free survival	→ Overall survival
Disease-specific mortality	
Cancer progression	
Occurrence of second malignancy	→ Cancer progression
Weakened heart / heart failure	→ Cardiac outcomes
Anxiety	
Depression	→ Psychological distress
PTSD and PTSS	

The Initial COS is shown in Figure 6.

The Initial COS consists of 15 CORE domains (to be measured at all time point across AYA cancer care), 3 additional ON treatment domains, and 3 additional OFF treatment domains. The inclusion of both ON and OFF treatment domains is to recognise that an outcome’s perceived importance will vary based on the patient’s treatment phase. Some CORE domains will also vary depending on treatment phase, but it is how they are measured that will overcome this.

Figure 6: The Initial COS for AYAs (aged 15-39) with cancer

Future Work

Moving forward, the Initial COS will be used for implementation, in line with the STRONG AYA protocol. Meanwhile, WP1 will continue developing the Final COS, in line with scientific methodology. This includes completing round 3 of the Delphi survey.

A final core measurement set will also be developed to match the outcomes in the final COS, in line with scientific methodology.

6 Conclusion

The Initial COS has been developed pragmatically for initial implementation throughout the healthcare research ecosystem in future work packages in the STRONG AYA project. It takes into account the viewpoints of all three stakeholder groups, and the consensus meeting resulted in decisions being made about the finalised Initial COS items. Work will continue to develop the Final COS, based on scientific literature; this includes completing Round 3 of the Delphi survey and finalising the Core Measurement Set.

7 Repository for primary data (annex)

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